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Battery-hydrogen vs. flywheel-battery hybrid storage systems for renewable energy integration in mini-grid: A techno-economic comparison

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ABSTRACT

Decentralized renewables power production is rapidly growing because of environmental concerns. With the purpose of maximizing renewable exploitation, energy storage systems integration in Mini-Grids (MGs) is needed. Hybrid energy storage systems (HESSs) are promising to obtain enhanced performances in terms of both capacity and responsiveness, yet their feasibility may be hindered by design and management choices impacting the economic competitiveness. In this paper, two HESSs are analysed and compared in a real case-study, namely reversible solid oxide cell (rSOC)/Li-ion battery and flywheel/Li-ion battery systems. The analysis here developed handles annual photovoltaic generation and electric load actual dataset and includes: i) a statistical analysis to obtain the most representative days, ii) dynamic modeling of the HESSs, iii) simulations to define components sizing and to extrapolate the evolution of annual battery state-of-charge, iv) battery lifespan assessment through application of the rainflow cycle counting algorithm, and v) a detailed economic evaluation (Levelized Cost of energy LCOE, Levelized cost of Storage LCOS and their sensitivity to electricity market price) including subsidies for self-consumption. For both HESSs, performance indexes of reduction of energy withdrawal from the grid and self-consumption increase are fixed at about 30 % and 70 % respectively, with reference to the features of the investigated MG. As main outcomes for this integrated methodology, it appears that self-consumption rewards (i. e. 110 €/MWh) let the flywheel/Li-ion battery HESS reach a LCOS agreeing with 2021 average market parity. On the contrary, LCOS is more than two-fold for the rSOC/Li-ion battery HESS, being equal the impact on the MG management and its energy independence from the main power grid. The integrated methodology is adequate for critically reviewing design and management choices and understanding the impact of the market on the profitability of a sub-system, with insight on energy storage units.

1. Introduction

The world energy system is rapidly growing mainly due to the implementation of renewable energy sources. Solar Photovoltaic panels (PV) and wind turbines are increasing their contribution to the energy mix of all communities and are expected to rise shortly. Since those technologies produce electricity, the main impact falls on the electrical grid. In fact, solar and wind are unpredictable energy sources and cause stress on the electric grid as it operates to date. Moreover, renewables are distributed energy sources, thus their expected high penetration needs a reconfiguration of the grid [1]. In this framework, decentralized

power generation from renewables allows also to extend electrification to remote and rural areas, as analysed in [2,3]. Hence, in this context electrical grids are evolving towards a new generation design to support the introduction of fluctuant electricity, namely the “smart grid” model [4]. A smart grid integrates and optimises loads and energy production at the local level, considering the final elements connected to the grid not only as users but as producers and consumers (prosumers) at the same time. Thus, research efforts are focussing in reducing energy transmission losses, necessary for local operations, and supporting energy optimisation at micro and Mini-Grid (MG) levels.

Integrating renewable energy in MGs requires the installation of

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energy storage systems in a distributed manner to allow the postponed use of energy with respect to its generation. At the local level, the leading technologies with sufficient maturity for a real application in micro- and mini-grids are batteries, flywheels, supercapacitors and hydrogen [5]. The main concern is that such technologies have characteristics suitable for specific purposes. For example, hydrogen guarantees long-term storage but low round-trip efficiency. In contrast, batteries have very high efficiency but capacity-to-power ratio suitable for short- and mid-term storage, and flywheels and supercapacitors show high power density but low storage timeframes [6–7]. In this framework, batteries have become the prevailing energy storage system thanks to their high efficiencies, reliability, and scalability. Among the different battery technologies, Li-ion batteries dominate in the current applications since they feature high efficiencies, high energy densities, reliability and high cycle lifespans.

With the aim of optimising the technology's features, a significant upgrade comes from the hybridisation of the different technologies. It allows answering the energy demand under optimized performance at different timescales. It follows that energy efficiency and devices lifespan are greater than the one of base technologies when operate in a not hybrid configuration. Therefore, the hybridisation of different technologies brings new and innovative challenges and opportunities both at the technical and, consequently, economic levels, as also demonstrated in [8].

Looking at the economic aspect, the impacts of energy storage introduction can be studied with the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) or similar indexes [9]. In the current practice, LCOE accounts for the overall costs faced for energy generation and supply. When LCOE is applied to evaluate the average cost of electricity supplied in a grid-connected system equipped locally with renewable energy generators, the net energy trade with the main power grid impacts the final price of supply. Conversely, LCOE directly measures on-site generation cost when the MG reaches 100 % energy independence (or when the MG is stand-alone [10]). According to the IRENA database, the LCOE of solar PV has decreased from 0.381 USD/kWh to 0.057 USD/kWh in the last decade [11]. The comprehensive LCOE of a MG with PV generators is expected to be higher, according to the capacity factor of the system and the load satisfaction rate. Energy imports and storages increase the value of LCOE yet allow to operate the grid with significant flexibility and resiliency.

1.1. Scope of the paper

This paper analyses a case study based on a real mini-grid where hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) are implemented, namely two battery-flywheel and battery-hydrogen are designed to be integrated into the existing mini-grid equipped with a PV plant. Two indexes are considered to evaluate the MG independence from the primary grid once energy storage is integrated: the reduction of the grid energy withdrawal and the increase in MG energy self-consumption, both assessed with respect to the case of energy storage absence. The two hybrid solutions are sized to reach the same performance of the MG regarding these indexes. This approach is chosen since the impact of energy storage implementation on the mini-grid performance is considered more suitable than specific sizing features (e.g., same installed power or capacity), aiming to produce a comparative economic assessment of two solutions with technical characteristics and applications significantly different each other. This characterises the present approach with respect to previous works of the authors [3,6,7] and others available in the literature [14–22]. Then, the two solutions are compared in terms of LCOE. To the best of our knowledge, an in-depth techno-economic comparison, on consistent basis, between two different hybrid energy storage solutions (i.e., hydrogen-battery and flywheel-battery) for a real MG application has never been presented in literature to date.

The study is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the mini-grid layout and a statistical method to analyse data from the field; Section

3 provides the investigation methodology for technical and economic aspects, while obtained results are presented in Section 4. Conclusive remarks are discussed in Section 5.

2. Mini-grid layout and statistical analysis on gathered data

According to Fig. 1, the MG consists of a PV power plant of 245 kWp, connected to a common AC bus through an inverter in order to satisfy the local load. The HESS is interfaced with the AC bus through inverters. Two different HESS configurations are considered. The first one hybridises a Li-ion battery technology with the flywheel one, while the second hybrid architecture integrates the battery coupled to a reversible solid oxide (rSOC) system. The connection to the medium-voltage grid is carried out through a transformer.

ASM Terni S.p.A. gathered and collected PV and load profiles in the MG under investigation. The MG annual power profile *diff* (i.e., the instantaneous difference between the PV generation and the load, as illustrated in Fig. 2) is considered for the HESS units' sizing and the subsequent economic comparison. The period at which the data were sampled was of 10 min. Subsequently, the power profile was expanded in MATLAB® R2019a ([23]) using linear interpolation to reach a 1 s time step according to the simulation requirements.

All the collected data were processed through a statistical procedure aiming to define the most representative days all over the year, as described below.

First, three power profiles have been considered: the original and two additional power profiles. One corresponds to the positive unbalance (surplus of renewable production), and one to the negative unbalance (lack of renewable production). To characterize the dynamic behavior of these profiles, specific parameters were defined to adequately describe the variability of operating conditions on a daily basis over a year. The defined parameters are:

- the daily mean power;

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the considered Mini-Grid.

Fig. 2. Annual power profile of the difference between PV generation and local load.

- the daily power bandwidth, calculated as the difference between the daily maximum and minimum recorded values;
- the ratio between the daily bandwidth and the mean power, which represents how wide the spread of instantaneous power values around the mean is;
- the daily mean power ramp, determined as the average value of the power ramp profile. This is the difference between two consecutive power values, as the measure of the instantaneous power fluctuation.

The parameters listed above were evaluated for each power profile. The representative days were individuated as the most stressful operational conditions for the energy storage devices, according to the following criteria:

1. days with the maximum bandwidth;
2. days with the maximum mean power;
3. days with the maximum ratio between the bandwidth and the mean power;
4. days with the minimum ratio between the bandwidth and the mean power;
5. days with the maximum power ramp.

15 days were extracted, considering the three aforementioned profiles, and then reduced to 11 since some days were the same. Fig. 3

depicts the corresponding *diff* daily profiles.

3. Modeling and techno-economic methodology

3.1. HESS sizing procedure

To compare hybrid energy storage systems based on very different technologies, usually with opposite application purposes in terms of the power management and the storage timeframe as the main features, a proper sizing procedure was defined. Indeed, flywheel and rSOC are very different technologies. As regards flywheel, it is a power-intensive technology generally employed in power smoothing applications providing high capabilities for short-term response. Vice versa, rSOC technology needs to avoid thermal cycling as a consequence of load modulation. Thus, rSOCs are generally operated at constant current densities in order to avoid any damage. Consequently, the power management strategies have to be implemented according to the specific HESS technology, as described below. Furthermore, it must be highlighted that Li-ion battery plays a crucial role in the studied application, moving from HESS energy intensive to power intensive unit when coupled to flywheel and rSOC, respectively. Below are some details regarding the investigated energy storage technologies:

Fig. 3. Selected daily power *diff* profiles (difference between PV generated power and load)

- LiFePO₄ (LFP) battery for both the hybrid storage systems; LFP battery specifications are deduced from [24]. This chemistry can provide high discharge powers (up to 2C) [25] with charge power limited to 1C. At the same time, its main limitation is due to a lower energy density (80–110 Wh/kg) with respect to other Li-ion battery technologies [26].
- Mechanical flywheel, whose features are fast responsiveness, long cycling life and high power densities [27]. Nevertheless, flywheel energy density is very low, especially for what concerns mechanical flywheels with non-magnetic bearings. Therefore, they are generally employed for short-term applications, such as power smoothing. A low-speed mechanical flywheel made of steel with ceramic bearings was considered in such work. Its operating speed range is 3500–8500 rpm.
- A rSOC stack, which can produce hydrogen exploiting electricity generation surplus and electricity in case of generation lack by consuming hydrogen. This technology can achieve round trip efficiencies between 38 and 48 %, as indicated in [28], and leveled storage costs competitive with other storage devices [29].

Regarding the developed sizing procedure, firstly the same HESS installed power is assumed equal to the generation peak power (245 kW). Then, several simulations over the selected days are performed varying the installed nominal power between the HESS components (being always constant the PV installed power, 245 kW). Finally, the optimal capacity for both HESSs is found for the equal results of MG performance indexes, a defined as it follows in Eqs. (1)–(2):

- a. reduction of energy withdrawal from the grid (I_1 , absolute percentage value):

$$I_1 = \left| \frac{E_{fromgrid} - E_{diff,neg}}{E_{diff,neg}} \right| (\%) \quad (1)$$

- b. self-consumption increase (I_2 , absolute percentage value):

$$I_2 = \left| \frac{E_{togrid} - E_{diff,pos}}{E_{diff,pos}} \right| (\%) \quad (2)$$

where $E_{diff,pos}$ and $E_{diff,neg}$ are the integral values of the positive and negative part respectively of the *diff* power profile, thus corresponding to the daily required/provided energy from/to the main grid in case of storage absence; $E_{fromgrid}$ and E_{togrid} represent the energy withdrawn/absorbed from the main grid, assessed as the integral of the corresponding power profiles obtained in the case of HESS integration in the investigated MG. Such indexes allow consistent comparison of the comparing two HESSs. Aiming at the HESSs sizing, in order to reach a good trade-off between the HESS capital costs and the MG performance, mean values over the 11 selected days of at least $I_1=30\%$ and $I_2=70\%$ are assumed, for the grid energy withdrawal reduction and the self-consumption increase respectively.

3.2. Systems modeling

In this paragraph, the modeling procedure for both HESSs is illustrated. In detail, the flywheel-battery HESS model is described in subparagraph a). Subparagraph b) reports the rSOC-battery implementation, focusing on the rSOC governing mathematical equations and the activation logic. The control logic is summarised in subparagraph c). Sections d) and e) define the methodology developed for rainflow cycle counting algorithm and for the techno-economic assessment, respectively.

3.2.1. Flywheel-battery hybrid storage system

The flywheel-battery-based HESS layout is depicted in Fig. 4, as implemented in the Simulink environment. The main sections of the dynamic model are highlighted in different colors. Specifically, the input power profile *diff* is implemented in the cyan sub-system; the power management section in grey and the battery and flywheel subsystems in red and dark green colors, respectively. Furthermore, a simultaneous perturbation stochastic approximation (SPSA) algorithm dedicated to the fast computation of the power shares among the HESS and the main

Fig. 4. Simulink flywheel-battery model layout.

grid is implemented in the magenta section. As regards the HESS subsystem, all the modeling details are deeply analysed in [30].

3.2.2. rSOC-Battery hybrid storage system

The developed model concerning the rSOC-battery HESS is illustrated in Fig. 5. In detail, the blue section represents the daily power profile *diff* provided as input to the control logic section. The power management strategy considers the current rSOC power and battery state of charge (SoC). The battery and rSOC subsystems are represented in orange and cyan on the right side. Moreover, a suitable control logic (see green section) is developed to define the rSOC activation timing.

Specifically, the battery model is developed with reference to what is presented in [30]. Then, a rSOC model is developed in the MATLAB®/Simulink environment, grounding on the following mathematical equations (Eqs. (3)–(9)) [31].

As depicted in Fig. 6, the following inputs are implemented in the model, according to the operating mode:

- Electrical power demand/supply;
- Hydrogen molar flow rate (SOFC);
- Oxygen molar flow rate (SOFC);
- Steam molar flow rate (SOEC);
- The standard open-circuit voltage E_0 .

Concerning the outputs, the model provides:

- the evolution of current and voltage delivered by the rSOC;
- the molar flow rates of products and reagents.

An rSOC stack requires a certain time to reach new operating conditions. This delay is caused by many factors, such as the non-instantaneous change of fuel and oxidant flows, the electrochemical reactions activation delay, and the required time for the conversion of the feeding fuel in hydrogen (whether a reformer is installed in the system for the operation with C-based fuels) [31]. Therefore, in this research the rSOC dynamic model is built on the following assumptions:

- the cells feeding gases (pure hydrogen and air) are considered to have an ideal behavior;

- the stack feeding channels sizing is likely to neglect the pressure drop across the stack;
- the feeding channels are considered “choked” because the pressure difference upstream and downstream the stack is noteworthy;
- constant operating temperature (maintained by the cooling system);
- negligible pressure losses in the electrodes.

The Nernst equation (Eq. (9)) is used to calculate the cell ideal voltage. Then, the real voltage is obtained considering ohmic and activation losses as function of the stack current. Concentration losses can be considered negligible since the stack works at low current density (fixed at 500 mA/cm² for both electrolysis and fuel cell mode), as discussed in [32]. The rSOC operating temperature is assumed equal to 750 °C. The model equations are shown below.

First, the dynamic characterisation of the feeding flow (hydrogen in fuel cell and steam in electrolysis respectively) is implemented. Specifically, the relationship between the hydrogen molar flow (q_{H_2} (kmol/s)) through the valve and its partial pressure (p_{H_2} (atm)) inside the electrode channel can be expressed according to Eq. (3) from [31], where K_{H_2} and M_{H_2} are the valve constant (kmol/(s atm)) and the gas molar mass (kg/kmol) respectively and U_f is the utilisation factor (equal to 0.8), as reported in [33].

$$\frac{q_{H_2}}{p_{H_2}} = \frac{1}{U_f} K_{H_2} \sqrt{M_{H_2}} \quad (3)$$

The hydrogen molar flow is identified by three flows, i.e. hydrogen input flow ($q_{H_2}^{in}$), hydrogen output flow ($q_{H_2}^{out}$) and hydrogen flow during the electrochemical reaction ($q_{H_2}^r$) [31]. The relationship among these factors is described in Eq. (4), where T (K) is the temperature of the hydrogen feeding flow and V_{an} (l) the anode volume.

$$\frac{d}{dt} p_{H_2} = \frac{RT}{V_{an}} (q_{H_2}^{in} - q_{H_2}^{out} - q_{H_2}^r) \quad (4)$$

According to the electrochemical relation between the hydrogen flow and the system current (rSOC operates in fuel cell mode), the flow rate of reacted hydrogen is expressed by Eq. (5) [31], where N_0 and I (A) indicate the number of stacked cells and the stack current respectively, F (C/kmol) is the Faraday's constant and K_r (kmol/(s A)) is a modeling constant.

Fig. 5. Schematic view of the rSOC-battery dynamic model.

Fig. 6. Overview of the ReSOC model and its inputs and outputs.

$$q_{H_2}^r = \frac{N_0 I}{2F} = 2K_r I \quad (5)$$

Through Eqs. (3)–(5) and applying Laplace's transform, the hydrogen partial pressure can be expressed in the time domain by Eq. (6) [31], with τ_{H_2} expressed by Eq. (7).

$$p_{H_2} = \frac{1/K_{H_2}}{1 + \tau_{H_2} s} (q_{H_2}^{in} - 2K_r I) \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{H_2} = \frac{V_{an}}{K_{H_2} RT} s \quad (7)$$

Likewise, through Eqs. (3)–(7), the inlet oxygen partial pressure and the produced water partial pressure can be obtained in fuel cell mode. On the other hand, the same procedure can be used to compute the required steam input during electrolysis (i.e. steam), applying Eq. (3) to steam (H_2O) and considering a utilisation factor U_f equal to 0.6 [33]. The polarisation curve for the rSOC was obtained, in the Simulink model, as the sum of two terms: the ideal Nernst's voltage (E) and the losses term (η) that includes the activation overvoltage (η_{act}) and the ohmic overvoltage (η_{ohmic}).

$$V_{cell} = E + \eta_{act} + \eta_{ohmic} = E + \eta \quad (8)$$

Since the stack is operated at constant current density, the voltage losses η were implemented as constant values deduced from an experimental campaign, for electrolysis and fuel cell modes respectively. Specifically, according to the defined current density and operating

temperature (Table 1), η corresponds to +0.44 V and –0.22 V, namely for SOEC and SOFC operations. The Nernst's instantaneous voltage is deduced from Eq. (9) [31], where E_0 represents the standard open circuit voltage (V).

$$E = N_0 \left[E_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{p_{H_2} p_{O_2}^{0.5}}{p_{H_2O}} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

It must be noted that during SOEC operating mode the partial pressures of the products and reactants must be inverted in Eq. (9). Furthermore, in SOEC mode a compressor efficiency of 0.8 is considered. Fig. 7 depicts the specific subsection relating to rSOC modeling. In detail, losses are calculated in the green subsystem and Nernst voltage is computed in the blue section. Table 1 lists the parameters implemented in the rSOC model.

3.2.3. HESS power management strategies

a) Flywheel-battery HESS

The power management strategy (PMS) implemented for flywheel-battery HESS was based on the SPSA algorithm. This algorithm presents great advantages, such as ease of implementation, robustness and online operating conditions [34]. In this paper, the SPSA implementation follows the procedure already presented and detailed in [35,36].

b) rSOC-battery HESS

Concerning rSOC-battery HESS in Fig. 8, the main cases defined by the PMS are illustrated. The PMS considers the current status of the variables listed below:

- the instantaneous power difference between the power profile ($diff$) and the rSOC power (P_{stack});
- the instantaneous operating mode of the rSOC power (SOEC corresponds to negative values, SOFC to positive ones);
- current battery state of charge (SoC). In reference to LFP battery specifications [26], the battery minimum SoC is fixed at 10 %.

According to such inputs, the PMS generates the power exchanges among the load, the HESS devices and - when required - the grid. Moreover, there is the constraint of only one daily switch for the rSOC operation, according to a suitable developed activation logic. This logic allows a proper switching when the PV production reaches a power threshold (PV generation higher than 45 kW). Four different macro-

Table 1
Input parameters for the implemented ReSOC model, deduced from [31].

Faraday's constant (F)	96,484,600 (C/(kmol))
Universal gas constant (R)	8314.47 (J/(kmol K))
K_r constant = $N_0/4F$	1.5547×10^{-7} (kmol/(s A))
Hydrogen time constant (τ_{H_2})	26.1 (s)
Hydrogen valve constant (K_{H_2})	8.43×10^{-4} (kmol/(s atm))
Oxygen time constant (τ_{O_2})	2.91 (s)
Oxygen valve constant (K_{O_2})	2.52×10^{-3} (kmol/(s atm))
Water time constant (τ_{H_2O})	78.3 (s)
Water valve constant (K_{H_2O})	2.81×10^{-4} (kmol/(s atm))
Standard open circuit voltage (E_0)	1.0058 (V)
Cell voltage loss SOEC (η_{SOEC})	0.22 (V)
Cell voltage loss SOFC (η_{SOFC})	-0.44 (V)
Number of cells in series (N_0)	60
Current density (CD)	500 (mA/cm ²)
Cell area (A_{cell})	2072 (cm ²)
Operating temperature (T)	750 (°C)
Utilisation factor (U_f)	0.6 (SOEC) / 0.8 (SOFC)
Compressor efficiency (η_{comp})	0.8

Fig. 7. Subsystem of the ReSOC stack.

Fig. 8. Detailed cases of the power management strategy (a negative value for the battery power corresponds to charge, a positive to discharge; in the case of grid power, a positive value means that the power is withdrawn from the grid, vice versa, a negative value means that the power is absorbed by the grid).

cases are defined:

- case 1: instantaneous negative *diff* power profile (i.e., PV production lower than load) is lower than rSOC stack power; according to battery SoC and rSOC operation mode (SOEC or SOFC), the control logic computes MG power shares according to the sub-cases 1.1–1.4 detailed in Fig. 8. Specifically, when the rSOC works as fuel cell

($P_{ReSOC} > 0$) and the battery is charged or partially charged (case 1.1), the latter provides the excess power by its discharge; otherwise (case 1.2), the power is withdrawn from the grid. On the other hand, when the rSOC works as electrolyzer ($P_{ReSOC} < 0$) with charged or partially charged battery (case 1.3), the latter provides the power discharging itself (assisted by the grid when the required power

overcomes the maximum battery power); otherwise (case 1.4), the excess of power is provided by the grid.

- case 2: instantaneous negative *diff* power profile is higher than rSOC stack power; taking into account battery SoC and rSOC operating mode, the control logic computes MG power shares according to the sub-cases 2.1–2.4 detailed in Fig. 8. In detail, when the rSOC works as fuel cell ($P_{ReSOC} > 0$) and the battery is charged or partially charged (case 2.1), the latter absorbs the excess power for its charging (or partially sent to the grid if the power exceeds the maximum battery charge power); vice versa (case 2.2), the excess of power is sent to the grid. On the other hand, when the rSOC works as electrolyzer ($P_{ReSOC} < 0$) with charged or partially charged battery (case 2.3), the latter provides the power discharging itself (assisted by the grid when the required power overcomes the maximum battery power); otherwise (case 2.4), the excess of power is provided by the grid.
- case 3: instantaneous positive *diff* power profile (surplus of PV generation with respect to the load) is lower than rSOC stack power; Fig. 8 illustrates the sub-cases 3.1–3.4 considered by the control logic for the calculation of the MG power shares. In such case, when the rSOC works as fuel cell ($P_{ReSOC} > 0$) and the battery is discharged or partially charged (case 3.1), the exceeding power is used for battery charging; vice versa (case 3.2), the excess of power is sent to the grid. On the other hand, when the rSOC works as electrolyzer ($P_{ReSOC} < 0$) with charged (fully or partially) battery (case 3.3), the latter provides the required exceeding power discharging itself (assisted by the grid when the required power overcomes the maximum battery power); otherwise (case 3.4), such amount is completely withdrawn from the grid.
- case 4: positive *diff* profile is higher than rSOC stack power; also, for case 4, four sub-cases (4.1–4.4) are considered. When the rSOC works as fuel cell ($P_{ReSOC} > 0$) and the battery is discharged or partially charged (case 4.1), the latter absorbs the excess power for its charging (or partially sent to the grid if the power exceeds the maximum battery charge power); vice versa (case 4.2), the excess of power is sent to the grid. On the other hand, when the rSOC works as electrolyzer ($P_{ReSOC} < 0$) with discharged or partially charged battery (case 4.3), the power is used for its charge (assisted by the grid when the required power overcomes the maximum battery power); otherwise (case 4.4), the excess of power is absorbed by the grid.

3.2.4. Rainflow cycle counting

The procedure for determining the annual battery SoC profiles (for both HESSs) is explained below. First, the annual day-by-day *diff* power profile was sorted into classes corresponding to the daily hours, from 0 to 12, in which *diff* is positive (i.e., PV production is higher than load). Subsequently, it was determined the yearly occurrences of the classes. Finally, the correspondence between classes and the selected days, individuated in Section 2, is summarised in Table 2.

The aim is to build the yearly SoC profile based on the simulation outcomes obtained for the 11 selected days. The SoC profile is used as input to the rainflow cycle counting (RFC) algorithm. From Table 2, it is evident that the selected days do not correspond with classes 6,7,10 and

Table 2
Annual occurrences of the selected days.

Class (h per day)	Annual occurrences	Selected day
0	25	2
1	31	7
2	25	4, 11
3	24	3
4	24	5
5	39	8
8	50	9
9	37	1, 10
11	1	6

12. Therefore, summing up the third column of Table 2, the resulting number of days is lower than 365. Subsequently, class #3 is repeated three times to extend the SoC profile to one year. The repetition of this class is assumed under a restrictive hypothesis, being one of the classes with lower daily PV production. The daily simulations are carried out for all the considered days starting with a battery SoC equal to 10 %. Subsequently, the SoC vectors are repeated according to their corresponding number of annual occurrences to build the yearly SoC profile. The simulations are performed both HESSs. Therefore, two different annual SoC profiles are obtained and used as inputs for RFC analysis. RFC represents a common and powerful tool for battery lifespan estimation [8–19]. However, it often provides an overestimated lifespan since it does not consider critical issues such as electrolyte degradation, temperature effects and self-discharge. This method is based on counting the charge/discharge cycles Z_i for one year; Z_i cycles are categorized according to m intervals of the full range of depth of discharge (DoD). By comparing the number of cycles performed during the year at a certain depth of discharge (Z_i) with the corresponding Cycle to Failure (CF_i) of the considered battery technology, it is possible to estimate the useful life of the battery, Eq. (10):

$$Lif e_{batt} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{Z_i}{CF_i}} \quad (10)$$

3.2.5. Techno-economic procedure

The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is taken as a comparison term since it is a widely shared metric for the synthetic economic evaluation of different energy system assets.

LCOE is generally calculated with the standardised definition ([37]) reported in Eq. (11) and represents the average cost of electricity consumed at the load side during the lifetime of the project (n , duration in years). During n years, several costs occur: the initial investment at the very beginning ($I_{sys,0}$, due to the installation of q components, Eq. (12)), and all annual costs related to the system operation ($C_{sys,i}$). Yearly, $C_{sys,i}$ consists of the sum of i^{th} costs related to external energy supply ($E_{ext,i}$), plus replacement ($R_{k,i}$) and operation & maintenance ($O \& M_{k,i}$) costs related to each k^{th} system component (Eq. (13)). The Net present value of all system costs is divided by the total load energy demand (E_L). Annual costs and annual energy flows are referred to the project begin at a discount rate r .

$$LCOE = \frac{I_{sys,0} + \sum_{i=1}^n C_{sys,i} / (1+r)^i}{\sum_{i=1}^n E_{L,i} / (1+r)^i} \quad (11)$$

$$I_{sys,0} = \sum_{k=1}^q I_{k,0} \quad (12)$$

$$C_{sys,i} = E_{ext,i} + \sum_{k=1}^q O \& M_{k,i} + R_{k,i} \quad (13)$$

Table 3 reports market reference values for the estimation of each cost item. The PV, the hydrogen storage and the LFP battery specific

Table 3
Cost items library.

Cost item	$I_{k,0}$	$O \& M_{k,i}$	$R_{k,i}$
PV	970 €/kWp	2 % I_{PV0}	none
LFP Battery	411 €/kWh	9 €/kWh	411 €/kWh
Flywheel	1593 €/kWh	0.0003 €/kWh	none
	162 €/kW		
rSOC system	2930 €/kW	25 €/kW	1800 €/kW
rSOC stack	(included in $I_{rSOC,sys,0}$)		1125 €/kW
Hydrogen storage	130 €/kWh	none	130 €/kWh
External energy supply	Costs from the electricity market [42]		

costs are recalled from technical reports, while specific costs for the rSOC and the flywheel are retrieved through a linear and exponential regression of data found in the literature (references for cost may be found at [38–41]).

Finally, the external energy supply is evaluated with regard to the electricity unique national price index (PUN), taken from historical data series from the Italian electric market [42]. It is noteworthy to mention that, due to the current energy crisis, such an index has quickly risen from the last months of 2021. Therefore, LCOE estimation based on the short-term PUN instability might lead to a fleeting outcome. For this reason, LCOE is also calculated regarding stable-market conditions PUN.

3.2.5.1. Auxiliary management metrics. To the end of the proposed case analysis, the initial investment is calculated considering two major sources of expense, namely the installation costs for the PV section and those related to the energy storage section. Then, each part of the system requires operation and maintenance at a cost rate that is technology-specific. Replacement costs are estimated considering the periodic reintegration of damaged parts, while the frequency of replacement is either calculated or referred to in literature data. Finally, the cost of external energy supply depends on two factors: the performance of the RES generator combined with the energy storage section and the cost of energy purchased from the grid. Thanks to the optimisation of the further, energy withdrawals from the main grid or integration with an external source can be substantially reduced. However, the latter is strongly related to the electricity market dynamics and, therefore, can markedly alter the final LCOE result notwithstanding the optimized MG design and management. In terms of number, these energy management performances are measured as Self-consumption ratio (σ , Eq. (14)), indicating the share of self-produced energy consumed within the MG bounds $E_{self-cons}$ out of the total amount available E_{PV} and Grid Dependence Rate (ζ_{grid} , Eq. (15)), comparing the net energy exchange between the main power grid and the MG $E_{from\ grid} - E_{to\ grid}$ with the MG total load E_{load} .

$$\sigma = \frac{E_{self-cons}}{E_{PV}} \quad (14)$$

$$\zeta_{grid} = \frac{E_{from\ grid} - E_{to\ grid}}{E_{load}} \quad (15)$$

In order to filter the effects of the market price and to evaluate the cost of self-produced energy, two modified levelized costs (LC) metrics are also calculated [9]:

- i) The Levelized Cost of Delivery (LCOD, Eq. (16)). This indicator compares the PV power generator costs with the total self-consumption, namely the direct consumption to satisfy the load demand and the share of energy delivered to the energy storage units for charging (since a charging storage is a virtual energy consumer). From Eqs. (14) and (16), it appears clearly that LCOD decreases with increasing self-consumption.
- ii) The Levelized Cost of Storage (LCOS, Eq. (17)). This metric evaluates the specific cost of stored energy, which is precious from the point of view of energy management. Therefore, LCOS compares the costs ascribed to the energy storage section with the total net stored energy that the system can deliver to the load while discharging.

$$LCOD = \frac{I_{PV,0} + \sum_{i=1}^n C_{PV,i} / (1+r)^i}{\sum_{i=1}^n E_{self-cons,i} / (1+r)^i} \quad (16)$$

$$LCOS = \frac{I_{HESS,0} + \sum_{i=1}^n C_{HESS,i} / (1+r)^i}{\sum_{i=1}^n E_{stored,i} / (1+r)^i} \quad (17)$$

These are to be considered together with the standard LCOE

indicator to have a complete overview of the economic value embedded in the system management.

3.2.5.2. Subsidies. In a given context, the Transmission System Operator (TSO) may reward the proficient management of sub-grids equipped with their own renewable power generator and self-consumption utilities groups. In this event, subsidies unburden the economic plan of the system. Then, to the end of the economic metrics calculations, these subsidies are calculated with the specific rules of the TSO, proportionally to Self-Consumption.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Sizing results

The simulations performed provide the final sizing of the energy storage devices, targeting at a 30 % reduction of the energy withdrawal from the grid (index I_1) and a 70 % self-consumption increase (index I_2) as mean values over the most representative selected days. Specifically:

- a. Battery-flywheel HESS. The LFP battery was sized with 260 kWh capacity. Although the LFP battery can be charged up to 1C and discharged up to 2C [24,25], dis-/charge powers were limited to 65 kW by the control logic in order to avoid high C-rates during charge and discharge processes. This was possible thanks to the flywheel, that reduces harmful power spikes otherwise required or provided to the battery. The flywheel was sized with 180 kW maximum power and 42 kWh capacity., considering an operating speed range of 3500–8500 rpm.
- b. rSOC-battery HESS. The rSOC features were assessed at 40–80 kW power for SOFC/SOEC modes respectively, and 450 kWh of installed storage capacity (corresponding to 13.5 kg_{H2} at 200 bar). In this HESS configuration, the LFP battery has to operate differently with respect to the flywheel-battery HESS. The LFP battery works absorbing or providing the power excess/lack according to the *diff* profile and rSOC constantly dis-/charges consuming (fuel cell mode) or producing hydrogen (electrolysis). Subsequently, a 160 kWh-capacity LFP battery was determined. The discharge power was limited through the PMS to 200 kW, while 1C charge power was considered. Fig. 9 depicts the simulated trends of the investigated MG parameters for both the considered HESSs, with reference to day 7, to provide an example of how storage devices are managed in the two hybrid architectures to match *diff* evolution.

Table 4 reports the results obtained, in terms of the MG energy balance, when the flywheel-battery HESS is integrated. Table 5 resumes the same data for the case of the rSOC-battery HESS. Indexes I_1 and I_2 are assessed accordingly to Eqs. (1) and (2), proving the targets achievement. It is remarked as this sizing procedure allows comparing different HESS architectures whose effectiveness in terms of MG independence degree is equal.

4.2. Rainflow cycle counting results

For several battery chemistries, the useful lifespan can be assessed according to their specific cycle-to-failure curve (see Fig. 10 for LFP chemistry). This curve is generally depicted as a curve showing the number of CF versus the battery DoD.

Therefore, according to Eq. (10), the estimated lifespan of the LFP battery was obtained according to the SoC evolution obtained through the MG dynamic simulation. The SoC profiles relative to the 11 simulated days are then elaborated in Section 3.4 to determine the SoC annual trend. Fig. 11 depicts the battery lifespan for the two investigated HESS configurations.

It must be emphasized that, the battery is less stressed in the

a)

b)

Fig. 9. Main simulation parameters relative to day 7 for the two considered hybrid energy storage systems: a) rSOC-battery and b) flywheel-battery.

Table 4
Energetic results and corresponding indices values for the simulated selected days, concerning flywheel-battery HESS.

Day	$ E_{diff, pos} $ (kWh)	$ E_{fromgrid} $ (kWh)	$ E_{diff, neg} $ (kWh)	$ E_{tograd} $ (kWh)	I_1	I_2
1	543	190	626	165	69.7 %	69.6 %
2	0	1960	2221	0	11.8 %	–
3	107	502	792	1	36.6 %	99.3 %
4	43	1157	1423	0	18.7 %	100.0 %
5	138	833	1169	0	28.8 %	99.9 %
6	1092	162	592	689	72.6 %	36.9 %
7	0	1515	1737	0	12.8 %	–
8	123	1038	1398	0	25.8 %	100.0 %
9	509	1133	1390	381	18.5 %	25.2 %
10	617	524	848	262	38.3 %	57.5 %
11	31	1727	2017	0	14.4 %	100.0 %
Mean					32 %	76 %

Table 5
Energetic results and corresponding indices values for the simulated selected days, concerning rSOC-battery HESS.

Day	$ E_{diff, pos} $ (kWh)	$ E_{fromgrid} $ (kWh)	$ E_{diff, neg} $ (kWh)	$ E_{tograd} $ (kWh)	I_1	I_2
1	543	206	626	135	67.2 %	75.2 %
2	0	1866	2221	0	15.9 %	–
3	107	550	792	0	30.6 %	100.0 %
4	43	1193	1423	0	16.2 %	100.0 %
5	138	926	1169	0	20.8 %	100.0 %
6	1092	15	592	541	97.5 %	50.5 %
7	0	1542	1737	0	11.2 %	–
8	123	1218	1398	0	12.9 %	100.0 %
9	509	948	1390	509	31.8 %	0.0 %
10	617	445	848	94	47.5 %	84.8 %
11	31	1807	2017	0	10.4 %	100.0 %
Mean					33 %	79 %

flywheel-battery HESS configuration since it works at lower C-rates thanks to the flywheel, than in the other HESS configuration. This is consistent with the resulting battery lifetime for flywheel-battery HESS higher than in the rSOC-battery configuration.

4.3. Techno-economic assessment and comparison

The techno-economic assessment is mainly based on the indicators ζ_{grid} , σ and LCOE. LCOE is calculated regarding the different system configurations investigated: the mini-grid with the flywheel-battery HESS, and the mini-grid with the rSOC-battery HESS.

The equipment costs are estimated from the reference data in previous Table 3, while the net energy balances are accounted yearly

(Table 6). The whole project is supposed to have a 25-year lifetime. Within this time horizon, the energy storage units components are replaced to guarantee good performances to the system. For simplicity, however, this model does not implement a continuous performance decay rate. The battery replacement frequency is shown in Fig. 11, while the flywheel lifetime is supposed to overcome 25 years, and the rSOC replacement frequency is calculated from typical degradation rates exhibited by state-of-the-art products [44].

From the data in Table 6, it is clear to notice that the utmost performance of any hybrid energy storage system installed in the given MG allows reaching a residual grid dependence of 48 %. In the event of no storage unit installed, the PV alone actually leaves about 69 % of the supply to the upper power grid. ζ_{grid} decreases as the energy storage retains some energy for a postponed utilisation (batteries and flywheels. $\zeta_{grid}=58.4$ %, rSOC and batteries $\zeta_{grid}=59.7$ %). This means that the final LCOE indicator calculated on the load supply is deeply influenced by the electricity market price. Fig. 12 reports the results obtained for the given system configurations in the event of an average electricity price of 0.125 €/kWh, which corresponds to the Italian market, to the mean value during all the year 2021 of the electricity unique national price index (PUN). The addition of energy storage units increases installation, maintenance, and replacement costs. Then, it sorts an increase of the LCOE compared to the baseline solution. Yet, the LCOE variations regarding the grid with no storage installed (PV) is reasonable. The rSOC and batteries HESS shows a higher LCOE (0.22 €/kWh) than the flywheel and batteries one (0.18 €/kWh). None of the systems proposed attains the market parity, and the results are rather far from the 2020 IRENA target for PV systems. This is also due to the limited share of self-produced energy on the user energy needs (see σ and residual ζ_{grid} from Table 6).

The introduction of energy storage units allows an internal control of the cost of electricity purchased by the users. As Fig. 13a reveals, the MG equipped with no storage is economically weaker in the event of a marked growth of the electricity market price, which has been significant since the latest months of 2021 and has become sharper due to the primary energy supply crisis in 2022. For what concerns the solution with PV and HESS rSOC+battery, the parity goal is attained when the market price is higher than 0.380 €/kWh. In addition, this energy storage system is competitive with the basic layout with only the PV generator in extreme events, when the market price rises over 0.600 €/kWh. Then, the LCOE parity between the system equipped with the PV generator and the one with PV and HESS batt+flyw is reached about a market price of 0.320 €/kWh, yet both solutions fall below the market parity threshold when the market price is in the range 0.210–0.250 €/kWh. The addition of this energy storage makes the mini-grid economically resilient in front of unpredictable and severe fluctuations. This outlook is fundamental for the strategic management of energy resources and power grids.

It is remarked that the economic profitability of energy storage can be increased whether remuneration of ancillary functions as additional flexibility in power and/or capacity is implemented. For instance, the piloting project of the Italian TSO Terna S.p.A. provides a similar reward for high power (> 50 MW) storage plants [45]. Concerning lower power MG scenario (according to Section 3.5 subparagraph “Subsidies”), the EU Clean Energy Package and the RED II have been fundamental to define a new subsidiary framework for renewable energy communities. Thereby, the new framework is likely to boost the energy storage economic profitability and its consequent broader implementation. In detail, looking at the implementation context of this study which includes multi-users MGs, self-consumption is rewarded with 110 €/MWh (Italian law DM 16/9/20) in case of renewable plants with an installed power suitable for the MG power range [46]. Therefore, if this bonus for self-consumption is included in the LCOE calculations, the convenience threshold changes as shown in Fig. 13b. the system with the PV alone gains advantages over the market from an electricity market price of 0.140 €/kWh. The system with PV and HESS battery+flywheel follows

Fig. 10. Cycle to failure curve used for LFP battery [43].

Fig. 11. Battery lifespan: results of the RFC analysis for the two studied HESSs.

Table 6
Annual energy balances.

	PV (MWh/ y)	LOAD (MWh/ y)	Net E_{grid} (MWh/ y)	Gross $E_{self-cons}$ (MWh/y)	ζ_{grid}	σ
1) No Storage	335.97	648.35	447.01	76.79	68.9 %	22.85 %
2) rSOC- battery			386.93	217.32	59.7 %	64.68 %
3) flywheel- battery			378.68	223.25	58.4 %	66.45 %

from 0.160 €/kWh, and the system with PV and HESS rSOC+battery from 0.270 €/kWh. The parity between the solution with and without energy storage is reached at 0.180 €/kWh and 0.450 €/kWh, for the HESS battery+flywheel and HESS rSOC+battery respectively. This kind of subsidy unburdens energy storage costs yet does not boost the convenience of storage against the solution with just the renewable generator installed. This is true because the maximum self-consumption rate is relatively low due to the sub-grid boundary conditions. In stable conditions in the electricity market (like in the five years 2016–2020), the average PUN index slightly fluctuated near 0.060 €/kWh. Consequently, none of the solutions investigated would have been competitive with the market provision.

Fig. 12. LCOE assessment. Electricity market price 0,125 €/kWh (average EU price in the latest 5 years).

Aiming at evaluating the specific costs of self-consumed and stored energy, the results of LCOD and LCOS are presented in Fig. 14. The influence of energy purchases from the market is excluded through these metrics. In other words, these indicators show the economic value of energy produced within the MG, as if a 100 % self-consumption rate is reached and no trade with the market occurs. Then, they should set an ideal goal to be reached with the management. Clearly, the introduction of HESS has a positive impact on LCOD reduction (from 0.38 €/kWh down to c.a. 0.13 €/kWh). If any self-consumption bonus is not rewarded (Fig. 14a), LCOD still exceeds the LCOE target set by IRENA for PV systems. However, when the self-consumption bonus is included, the goal is scored with an LCOD < 0.05 €/kWh (Fig. 14b). The LCOS of the investigated solutions decreases markedly in the subsidised framework and the results obtained are coherent with technical outlooks.

5. Conclusions and future outlooks

This paper shows a case study where hybrid energy storage systems are designed for an existing mini-grid equipped with a PV plant. To this purpose, two indexes are considered to evaluate the mini-grid independence from the primary grid once energy storage is integrated: the reduction of the grid energy withdrawal and the increase in energy self-consumption, both assessed with respect to the case of energy storage

Fig. 13. LCOE vs Electricity market price, trends: a) without self-consumption bonus, b) with GSE self-consumption bonus.

Fig. 14. LCOD and LCOS: a) without self-consumption bonus, b) with GSE self-consumption bonus.

absence. The two hybrid solutions are sized to reach the same performance of the mini-grid regarding these indexes. Regarding literature, this approach is chosen since the impact of energy storage implementation on the mini-grid performance is considered the utmost and truly relevant target, rather than specific sizing features (e.g. same installed power or capacity). The main outputs of the dynamic simulations (i.e. power exchanges and HESS state of charges) are implemented in the economic assessment. In particular, battery SoCs for both the architectures are used for battery lifespan evaluation (RFC algorithm is applied). The detailed economic methodology is developed to evaluate economic sustainability of HESSs introduction within the MG, which produces a three-fold magnitude increase of energy self-consumption with respect to the no-storage MG case. Although from the final user perspective the LCOE is still higher with respect to the basic PV mini-grid without storage (PV & HESS rSOC+battery vs. PV +51 %, PV & HESS flywheel+battery vs. PV +23 %), a different scenario arises when

self-consumption is rewarded. The marked increase in self-consumption finds an economic counterpart in the scenario with monetary reward to self-consumption, where levelized cost indicators fall below the target set by IRENA for PV-based mini-grids. Moreover, the economic performance significantly differs when the two investigated HESSs are compared under such assumption and at parity of effect on the MG, in terms of its energy independence from the main grid. Specifically, the HESS flywheel+battery would reach an LCOS agreeing with the average 2021 market parity. Conversely, LCOS would be more than two-fold for HESS rSOC+battery.

List of abbreviations

- CF Cycle to Failure
- DoD Depth of Discharge
- HESS Hybrid Energy Storage System

LC, Levelized Cost	
LCOD	Levelized Cost of Delivery
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage
MG	Mini-Grid
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PMS	Power Management Strategy
PV	Photovoltaic
RFC	Rainflow counting
rSOC	reversible Solid Oxide Cell
SoC	State of Charge
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolyzer Cell
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
TSO	Transmission System Operator

Credit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization, L.B.; methodology, A.B. and D.P.; software, A.B. and D.P.; validation, A.B., D.P., L.B. and A.O.; formal analysis, A.B., D.P., D.C., G.C. and A.O.; data provision, F.C. and F.S.; investigation, A.B., D. P. and D.C.; writing—original draft preparation, A.B., D.P. and G.C.; writing—review and editing, A.B, D.P. and L.B.; visualization, A.B. and D.P.; supervision, L.B.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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